

STRENGTH AND FRACTURE TOUGHNESS PROPERTIES OF OXIDATION RESISTANT HIGH-TEMPERATURE CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Oxidation resistant ceramic matrix composite systems reinforced by Si-Ti-C-O fiber (Tyranno®) produced by Ube Industries LTD with ceramic matrix are now under development. Configuration of the reinforcement is 3-D woven fabrics, product of Shikibo LTD. Polymer conversion (PC) and chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) techniques are utilized for matrix consolidation. The highest strength at ambient temperature reaches 404MPa for PC materials, almost twice of similar material developed by SEP, France. High-temperature testings at 1200°C exhibit a possibility of maintaining room temperature strength. High fracture toughness values around 30 MPa·m^{1/2} are also obtained.

1. Introduction

Ceramic matrix composites (CMC) are now considered to be the most promising candidate for the key material in the essence of high-tech product, such as hypersonic aircraft, space transportation systems, supersonic engines and efficient energy generators. In the case of aircraft-like applications, nose sections, thermal protection systems, or even some primary structures will be built by such exotic materials. Earlier applications of CMC to components of hot structures in aeroengines is expected since current carbon/carbon (C/C) materials are questionable to those portions due to their poor oxidation resistance. Henceforth, National Aerospace Laboratory of Japan (NAL), Ube Industries LTD, and Shikibo LTD are conducting a joint research program¹ for development and mechanical evaluation of ceramic matrix composite systems reinforced by 3-D fabrics with ceramic matrix.

Before going into a description of our material, a result of a brief literature survey in the other related material should be given. SEP, a French company and Du Pont in USA is now producing a Si-C-O fiber reinforced SiC composite system². They use 2-dimensional reinforcement configuration and CVI for matrix packing. They also produce C/SiC material for less oxidation environment. MAN, a German company is also developing similar C/SiC and SiC/SiC systems³ with a new CVI technique for shorter consolidation time. Another German activity by Dornier⁴ is being undertaken using polymer conversion from precursor slurry. In Japan, a similar material to ours is also being developed by Nippon Carbon Co. LTD⁵. However, the detail is not clear so far.

According to such a survey, it is clear that mechanical performances of those CMC materials are not fully satisfactory and that we have a good reason for our own development. In the current program, NAL is in charge of definition of basic idea and evaluation of mechanical properties, including tensile strengths, fracture toughness, interlaminar shear strengths and so on. Ube Industries LTD provides the fibers and conducts consolidation of matrix. Shikibo LTD weaves these fibers into 3-D reinforcing fabrics. The main feature of the present material systems is their extraordinary oxidation resistance comparing to common C/C without coating layers. Excellent strength properties at room temperature and around 1200°C are verified. Fracture toughness and some other properties are also obtained. Intensive efforts for improving the strength and for finding the way of real application particularly to Japan's space transportation system, HOPE, are being made currently.

2. Descriptions of Developed Materials

Developed composite materials of interest in this paper were fabricated in global two lots, in FY91 (Material ID: 01 - 04) and FY92 (Material ID: 05 - 08). Reinforcing fiber is Si-Ti-C-O (Tyranno®), product of Ube Industries. They have two types of fibers, S and LoxM, which were used for the lots in FY91 and FY92, respectively. Tyranno®-LoxM shows a higher strength around 1300°C than S-type due to its lower oxygen content, 13%. The reinforcement geometry is featured by orthogonal 3-D woven fabrics. Two types of fabrics referred as SCL and SC are used here which belong to the family of the orthogonal weaves. Filament number ratios in the x,y,z directions are (1:1:0.13) and (1:0.8:1) for SCL and SC fabrics, respectively. The xy plane coincides with the plate plane and so the z axis does with the translaminal direction. A volume fraction of fibers, V_f , to the occupied volume of fabrics is about 40% for each type. The sectional pictures of SCL04 and SC04 are shown in Figures 1 and 2 respectively where the weaving patterns can be well identified. Arc translaminal threads are unique feature of SC fabrics. Nominal sizes of woven preforms in mm are $240 \times 150 \times 6^t$ for SCL and $240 \times 240 \times 6^t$ for SC.

Matrix consolidation is done by 2 types of methods; one is polymer conversion (PC) technique and the other is chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) or deposition (CVD) technique. The present PC technique using some polymeric precursors close to Poly-titane-carbo-silane is conceptually similar to the fabrication process of C/C materials. Three combinations in precursor materials and interface treatment are tried for each lot, ID: 01, 02, 03 and ID: 05, 06, 07, respectively. These PC materials are considered to be our true goal for development since a fabrication cost is much lower than CVI material. CVI materials by Silane gas are labelled by ID's: 04 and 08. These systems are, therefore, similar products to a so-called SiC/SiC system (CERASEP®) by SEP.

Thus, 4 kinds of matrix materials, 2 types of reinforcement fabrics and 2 types of fibers comprise 16 groups of composites with the labels of SCL01 to SC08. Table 1 is shown for reference for material classification. Density is also indicated in Table 1 and small values around 1.7 - 1.8 are also a very favorable advantage of the present materials. Such a feature can be attributed to a microstructure of the matrix.

The most important advantage of the present materials is their high oxidation resistance relative

Figure 1. Sectional View of SCL04 Specimen

Figure 2. Sectional View of SC04 Specimen

Table 1. Classification and Density of the Present CMC Materials

Types ID	Reinf. Fiber	Fab. Year	Fab. Method	Density
SCL01	Tyranno	91	PC	1.73
- 02	S	↓	↓	1.70
- 03	8.5 μm	↓	↓	1.72
SCL04	1.6k	↓	CVI	1.26*
SC 01	↓	↓	PC	1.72
- 02	↓	↓	↓	1.61
- 03	↓	↓	↓	1.72
SC 04	↓	↓	CVI	1.64
SCL05	Tyranno	92	PC	1.774
- 06	LoxM	↓	↓	1.763
- 07	8.5 μm	↓	↓	1.757
SCL08	1.6k	↓	CVI	1.33*
SC 05	↓	↓	PC	1.754
- 06	↓	↓	↓	1.749
- 07	↓	↓	↓	1.789
SC 08	↓	↓	CVI	1.504

*: Different value is possible due to the other thickness definition

to common C/C systems without coating. Time histories in weight changes of the present materials and C/C in static 1000°C air are indicated in Figure 3. As observed, SC04 (CVI Material) exhibits null oxidation and SC01 to SC03 (PC Materials) show weight reduction to some extent depending on their carbon contents and no reduction after the saturated points whereas C/C without coating shows a rapid mass-disappearance curve by "burning". Differences in oxidation rate will be pretty much enhanced in high speed air flow in aircraft and engine applications.

3. Preparation of the Material into Specimens

The fabricated source plates are sliced into strips with 25mm width and they are milled into the dumbbell shape indicated in Figure 4 with a profiling template. Because the present matrix materials are very hard particularly for CVI grade and tough for milling, there exist many problems in machining. For PC materials it is easier to machine. An early effort for solving the machining problem has been conducted with success. For example, a screw cutting of the present materials is now possible for an application to Japan's space transportation system, HOPE.

The upper shape specimens in Figure 4 are for ambient testings and the lowers are for high temperature testings. Due to the reasons stated in Section 5, sectional area of central straight portions in high temperature specimens is reduced. Furthermore, some different lengths are chosen according to various experimental reasons.

4. Tensile Tests at Room Temperature and Discussions

Prepared specimens cut out from 16 types of source plates are subjected to tensile tests at ambient temperature by an Instron 8501 testing machine. Hydraulic grips are utilized with cardboard protection tabs. These paper tabs work well without any slip and can be considered as one of the key points in testing technique. A clip-on gage of a 25mm base length is employed for strain measurement. Except for initial several specimens, acoustic emission (AE) measurements are performed through SPARTAN AT and TRA 2.5 systems. In-situ observation of the side edge of the specimens is conducted for almost a half of all the tests by an optical fiber microscope. A picture of testing set-up is shown in Figure 5. Note that the clip on gage, the lens of optical fiber microscope and the AE sensors are attached to the specimen. For AE sensors, silicon grease is applied in order to maintain coupling with the coarse surface of the present materials. A vertical pair of AE sensors on the left side, RI15, is for location identification, and the single AE sensor on upper right is for frequency analysis.

An example of stress(load)-strain relationships are indicated in Figure 6 for the highest tensile strength specimen in FY91 lots. The specimen ID is SCL04-04, one of CVI materials. It is clearly understood that the highest strength reaches as high as 242MPa.

Figure 3. Weight Reduction Rate in 1000°C Air

Figure 4. Shape and Dimensions of Specimens at Ambient and High Temperature Tests

Figure 5 Tensile Testing Set-Up at Room Temperature

This data exceeds the current world championship data in commercially available material², 200MPa, of the aforementioned SEP SiC/SiC (CERASEP®). A scatter in the data of 4 pieces in SCL04 is rather small and their average reaches 226MPa. Although SCL04 material exhibits lower initial elastic modulus, its tangential modulus in nonlinear stage becomes larger than those moduli of CERASEP®. This fact might be ascribed to the difference in the reinforcement fabrics. Both strain levels in SCL04 for the starting point of nonlinearity and the failure are slightly larger. Although a graphical presentation is omitted here, the strengths of PC materials in FY91 lots are not so high as SCL04. The only comparable result is 186MPa for SCL03 where a scatter is very serious. According to these findings, PC materials in FY91 lots are far from a matured material system.

Strength properties have been enormously improved in FY92 lots. Figure 7 depicts stress(load)-strain relationships of the highest tensile strength among all specimens, SCL05-01 of PC material. The strength and ultimate strain reach 410MPa and 0.85%, respectively, which are extremely great for CMC materials having x and y reinforcing fibers. The average of 3 specimens fall 404MPa and this value implies a scatter is not serious. It is clear that an elastic modulus of this SCL05-01, 75GPa, is much lower than CERASEP value, 230GPa. Figure 8 indicates stress (load) - strain relationships of the highest tensile strength among CVI materials, SCL08-01. In this case, a shape of the curve is very unique and strength reaches 321MPa. Initial elastic modulus of this CVI material, 134GPa, is higher than PC material SCL05, and lower than CERASEP®. A strength scatter in SCL08 specimens turns out to be trivial.

Figure 6. Stress(Load)-Strain Relation for the Maximum Strength Specimen of CVI Material in FY91 Lots

Figure 7. Stress(Load)-Strain Relation for the Maximum Strength Specimen (SCL05:PC Material in FY92 Lots)

Figure 8. Stress(Load)-Strain Relation for CVI Material in FY92 Lots (SCL08-01)

All tensile strength data are summarized in Table 2 for the sake of quick reference. The averaged strengths over 100MPa are tabulated. It can be understood in general that SCL type of fabric provides higher strengths than SC type, whereas SC type exhibits more compatibility for near-net shape forming technology. By optimizing filament quantity in each direction, we could have the best compromised material between strength and shape forming. Shaded data in Table 2 correspond to the plotted group of the materials in Figures 6, 7 and 8. The other finding is that ultimate strains in SCL06 and 07 is rather small. The reason can be ascribed to serious filament undulation in the xy plane of these source plates probably due to a fabrication process. In SCL05, such undulation is mild and specimens can be cut out parallel to filaments within straight portions. Thus, some improvements for preventing filament undulation during matrix consolidation process will provide even higher strength.

Table 2 Summary of Strength Properties at Room Temperature (Average Values for 3 Data)

ID	Strength (MPa)	Ultimate Strain(%)	Initial Modulus(GPa)
SCL03	127.9	0.265	62.6
- 04 [*]	226.1	0.394	116.5
SC 04	204.4	0.342	103.9
SCL05	403.8	0.867	70.0
- 06	286.3	0.636	61.8
- 07	272.4	0.600	66.7
SCL08	311.2	0.817	140.2
SC 05	254.8	0.838	54.1
- 06	239.7	0.846	50.4
- 07	258.6	0.868	57.3
SC 08	195.1	0.605	91.6

*: Average of 4 Specimen Data

Acoustic emission measurements are performed for some specimens. Figure 9 depicts an example of strain vs. AE-hit data for the highest strength PC material, SCL05. In this system, definition of "hit" is almost identical to that of "event" in AE terminology. A clear change in AE-hit rate can be identified in Figure 9. Such behavior can be found in high-strength SCL materials without any exception. A bent point about 0.2% strain is not fully correlated with static stress-strain relationships. The most possible interpretation of this behavior is an indication of a generation rate change in matrix microcracks or micro-slips on fiber-matrix interface. However, this hypothesis has not been verified through an observation by an optical-fiber microscopy so far. Hence, more intensive correlation effort between microscopic and macroscopic behavior including AE properties is required.

Figure 9. AE (Hit) vs. Strain Relation for SCL05-02

Some orthotropic elastic properties are expected for the present composites because orthogonal 3-D fabrics are used as reinforcement. According to the filament quantity in each direction, a rough estimation is possible. SC materials would exhibit more anisotropic property than SCL which would be tetragonal symmetry. For more precise knowledge, orthotropic moduli are measured for SC03, PC material, and the results are plotted in Figure 10. They are obtained for 0°, 45° and 90° specimens. Elastic moduli, E_0 , E_{45} and E_{90} , are determined by strains up to 0.05%. Poisson's ratios, ν_L and ν_{45} are measured in special testings with clip-on gages for straight strip specimens before machining into the shape of Figure 4. In-plane shear modulus G_{LT} is calculated by the well-known formula as follows:

Figure 10. Orthotropic Elastic Properties of PC Material: SC03

$$G_{LT} = E_{45} / 2(1 + \nu_{45}) \quad (1)$$

Thus, 4 independent moduli of plane orthotropy are obtained and their off-axis values are calculated. Figure 10 depicts such results with the 5 experimental values indicated by filled legends. It is observed that a level of anisotropy is not so serious as common unidirectional carbon/epoxy composites. Note that E_0 of CVI materials indicated in Table 2, SCL04, SC04 and SCL08 are almost twice or more than SC03 value.

5. Description of High-Temperature Test and Discussions

High-temperature tensile strength tests up to 1300°C are tried through a high temperature testing system 8502-HT by Instron Inc. Figure 11 depicts a testing set-up with the high temperature furnace. A camera in front of the furnace is a sensor of an electro-optical extensometer, Zimmer 200X. Strain measurement is conducted through this system with a collimated mercury lamp and flags attached to the specimens. Tensile loads are actually introduced through the shoulder of machined metal grips into the specimens with the shape of Figure 4 lower. In order to avoid local force concentration, small strips of ceramic paper are inserted between the specimen and grips. A shape of the grip will appear in Figure 13 later. These grips are made of a molybdenum alloy and they are inserted into the heat zone. Therefore, the maximum allowable temperature is limited to 1300°C although the furnace itself is designed to reach 1900°C. In order to prevent oxidation in heating systems of the furnace, temperature elevation is usually conducted at vacuum less than 10^{-4} torr. The heating systems run according to a prepared temperature-time history program. Temperature is measured by a platinum-rhodium thermocouple just adjacent to the specimen. After 20 minutes holding at the target temperature, tensile tests are performed.

Two examples of obtained stress-strain relationships at 1200°C are indicated in Figure 12 for PC (SCL05) and CVI (SCL08) materials. In the result of SCL05-08, the final failure mode is not a tensile break in a parallel portion but a shear-out at the specimen shoulder. Thus, a partial load is still maintained after the peak value. An example of a picture of the shear-out failure at the shoulder is shown in Figure 13. Even after a reduction of the sectional area from 54mm^2 to 36mm^2 (nominal), such a failure mode occurred. Tensile strength of SCL05 at 1200°C is expected over 344MPa, an average of 2 shear-out strengths, and presumably close to the ambient value according to the trends in the other materials stated later. The maximum strain reaches almost 1.5% and modulus decreases from 70GPa to 29GPa probably due to combination of fiber and matrix behavior.

A tensile break occurred for CVI material of SCL08 by virtue of a sectional area reduction. At the original width of 9mm, the shear-out happened also. In this case, therefore, design improvement works well. It can be understood that tensile strength is almost the same as room temperature value whereas slight elongation increase, 1.15% at failure, is observed based on a comparison with Figure 8. A unique shape of the stress-strain curve is maintained at high temperature. Some unsmooth behavior in the curve could be probably attributed to local damage occurrence.

Figure 11. Testing Set-Up at High Temperature

Figure 12. Examples of Stress-Strain Relationships at 1200°C

Figure 13. Example of Shear-Out Failure at Specimen Shoulder at 1200°C

Typical high temperature strength results are summarized in Figure 14 where the strengths of single fiber of Tyranno® LoxM are also shown. Take a special care that strength scales for composites and fibers are different. Failure strain is plotted in a different scale, too. The high temperature results of SCL07 are similar to their ambient strengths although a presentation of their stress-strain diagrams are skipped. Even in other cases, ambient strengths are maintained at 1200°C so long as shear-out failure does not happen. This conclusion is compatible with the strength behavior of single fiber. Therefore, the true tensile strength of SCL05 could be expected to be in the level around 400MPa. Of course, this expectation must be verified by improved shape specimens in the future.

Only one tensile test was tried at 1300°C for SCL05-10 specimen. However, an earlier yield in gripping fixtures occurred and no tensile failure or even shear-out could be realized. The maximum stress level reached was 271MPa. Thus, improvements in specimen and fixture designs must be required including an adoption of higher level materials in loading fixture. The present SiC/SiC is naturally a very eligible candidate.

6. Fracture Toughness Tests at Room Temperature and Discussions

Fracture toughness of the present material is measured by 4 point bending of in-plane specimens with notch in a similar method to Reference 6. Figure 15 indicates the shape and schema of the test and a typical load deflection curve. Since the plate is thicker here, bending height is increased to 12mm for securing crack path. Nominal notch depth and width are 2.5mm and 1.0mm, respectively. The latter value is not fully satisfactory due to a thick slicer blade. A crack propagation length is monitored and measured by the optical fiber microscope system. For a data reduction, assumptions that a flat crack surface is coplanar with the notch and that its shape is rectangular are employed.

A typical result in Figure 15 is obtained for SC04, one of CVI materials. Loading and unloading cycles are applied to the specimen accompanied by crack length measurement. Serious loop behavior can be observed in the load-deflection curve. The first crack extension step is discarded for data reduction because of a dull notch front. The consecutive load, deflection and crack length data provide fracture toughness, K_{IR} , based on a hypothetical isotropic modulus here. The average of the indicated and other 2 specimens of SC04 yields to $39.9\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, much higher than reported data of $25\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$. For the highest static strength material, SCL05, we have $28.9\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ as an average of 4 specimens. A summary of all data is given in Table 3 where the average of each group of material is indicated.

Figure 14. Summary of High Temperature Strengths of the Present Composites and Reinforcing Fiber

Figure 15 Specimen Shape and Typical Result of Fracture Toughness Test by Bending

Table 3 Summary of Fracture Toughness Tests (K_{IR})

Mat. ID	K_{IR} $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$	Test Quant.	Mat. ID	K_{IR} $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$	Test Quant.
SCL01	19.8	3	SCL05	28.9	4
- 02	12.3	3	- 06	24.0	3
- 03	9.3	2	- 07	30.9	4
SCL04	-*	-	SCL08	36.6	2
SC 01	19.2	4	SC 05	31.4	4
- 02	14.0	6	- 06	27.2	4
- 03	19.8	3	- 07	31.6	5
SC 04	39.9	3	SC 08	11.2	4

* : Not Measured due to Consumption of Specimens

FY91 lots provide lower results except SC04 and FY92 lots do the value around $30\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ except SC08. Similar matrix systems, 02 and 06 reduce the toughness slightly.

It should be mentioned here that toughness tests by bending like Reference 6 is not fully confident for obtain stabilized K_{IR} in R-curve behavior. Thus, careful examination will be required in the future whether the present results are 100% reliable or not.

7. Results of Interlaminar Shear Strength

Interlaminar shear strengths (ILSS) are measured for FY92 materials through ASTM D2344-76, short beam shear method by 3 point bending. Bending moment is applied in the xz plane. In other words, shear failure is intended to occur parallel to the xy plane. Instron 4505 static testing machine is used like in the fracture toughness tests. Bending span is fixed to 20mm and nominal width is 7mm whereas some fluctuation is allowed for material economy sake. By values of the peak loads and sectional areas, it is easy to determine ILSS.

The average of 5 tests for each material is summarized in Table 4. It is clear that SC naturally gives larger ILSS than SCL according to translaminar filament quantity. Note that real ILSS failure mode does not always happen in SC materials. So, the real ILSS value of SC might be larger than indicated. It is remarkable that even the worst result of the present CMC exceeds the corresponding ILSS of C/C for HOPE candidate materials. This benefit is of course brought from an employment of 3-D fabric reinforcement.

8. Concluding Remarks

Oxidation resistant ceramic/ceramic composites made of Si-Ti-C-O fibers and 3-D fabric reinforcement are developed. Two types of matrix consolidation process, PC and CVI, are attempted. Room temperature strength of one type of PC materials reaches exceptionally high value of 400MPa in average, more than twice of the preceding CMC system by SEP. It is very meaningful that PC material realizes the best performance if we consider an incredibly high fabrication cost of CVI material. To the authors' knowledge, this material system is the ever first one to arrive at such high level as for PC material. Moreover, the present CMC shows a great ultimate strain about 0.9%. Another its advantage is lower density of 1.8 g/cm^3 . Preliminary high temperature strength tests at 1200°C reveal almost the same strengths of these materials so far as ambient strengths unless they fail in the shear-out mode. The fracture toughness tests exhibits K_{IR} of $40\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ in the highest case and $29\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ in the strongest case. Also, the present material shows a great advantage in interlaminar shear strength due to its 3-D reinforcement structure. An intensive effort for application of this CMC to the future space transportation system is undertaken in Japan.

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Table 4 Summary of Interlaminar Shear

Strengths Tests: Average of 5 Data			
Mat. ID	ILSS (MPa)	Mat. ID	ILSS (MPa)
SCL05	27.8	SC 05	34.5
- 06	21.3	- 06	37.5
- 07	29.7	- 07	38.0
SCL08	34.9	SC 08	36.9
C/C for HOPE Design [‡] : 10 ~ 21 MPa			

[‡]: Reference 7